

APPLICABILITY OF ISO 14125 FOR STEEL-COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

Houssin Wehbe¹, Sven Hartwig², Maja W. Kandula³, Klaus Dilger⁴

¹ Langer Kamp 8, 38106 Braunschweig, Germany, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institute of Joining and Welding Technology, h.wehbe@tu-braunschweig.de,

<https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/ifs/>

² Langer Kamp 8, 38106 Braunschweig, Germany, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institute of Joining and Welding Technology, s.hartwig@tu-braunschweig.de,

<https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/ifs/>

³ Langer Kamp 8, 38106 Braunschweig, Germany, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institute of Joining and Welding Technology, m.kandual@tu-braunschweig.de,

<https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/ifs/>

⁴ Langer Kamp 8, 38106 Braunschweig, Germany, Technische Universität Braunschweig, Institute of Joining and Welding Technology, k.dilger@tu-braunschweig.de,

<https://www.tu-braunschweig.de/ifs/>

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ABSTRACT

The application of local fibre-reinforced plastic patches on metal is one possibility to implement economic lightweight constructions. Since there are no standardised testing methods for this newly created material class, the comparability of different materials and the performance prediction is difficult. Furthermore, there are no characteristic values, which describe the hybrid composites. Applying known testing methods is possible but the anisotropy and the asymmetry of the samples exacerbate the result interpretation. In order to broaden the understanding of the hybrid structures and to initiate a first step towards a standardised testing process, the four-point bending test is used.

Therefore, three configurations with different proportions of the composite were assembled and investigated. However, the test setup enables the detection of differences between the configurations. Another challenge with one-sided patches is that the sample position may influence the bending result. The conclusion shows that the position does not affect the elastic region but the fracture behaviour. Samples with tension-loaded composites always fail in the boundary layer, regardless of the configuration, whereas compression-loaded composites merely push the fibres on each other. Moreover, the fracture behaviour is influenced by the load-to-support ratio. An increase in the ratio results in lower forces absorbed by the samples and thus not necessarily leading to a failure. In addition, the experimental setup for hybrids has to be optimised to ensure a minimum quality standard. For instance, the use of a touching position sensor to measure the deformation is not effective.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the years, hybrid structures, a combination of steel and fibre-reinforced plastics, have justifiably acquired a great importance in the automotive sector to reduce weights and meet the increased legal requirements regarding the emission of carbon dioxide. [1-5] Possible application areas for these hybrid structures are e.g. A- or B-pillars in car bodies. [6, 7] For instance, ILK from TU Dresden designed a hybrid A-pillar to reduce the weight and alongside the production complexity. [6] In comparison to conventional A-pillars, the new hybrid structure reduces the number of components in the assembly and the different components are boned during the shaping and forming process. Therefore, the weight of the body can be reduced by more than 5 kg with the new hybrid A-pillars. Tests also show that the performance could be increased by additional 25% compared to monolithic metal constructions [6]. Moreover, BMW uses hybrid structures (metal and carbon fibre-reinforced thermoplastics joined with an adhesive) for the B-pillar of the 7 Series to reduce the weight and to enhance the crash performance. [7]

However, the scientific investigations focus on both the adhesion between materials [8-13], especially on pre-treated surfaces [14-16] and on efficient manufacturing processes [17-19], whereas characteristic parameters to describe the mechanical behaviour of hybrids, especially in terms of pre-designing stages as needed in simulations, are not defined yet. Material tests usually provide mechanical parameters. Unfortunately, international testing standards cover either monolithic materials [20] or composites but no hybrids [21, 22].

As a result, this paper focuses on the bending load case due to most common application of hybrids in bending areas. It aims for a better understanding of the mechanical behaviour and examines the applicability of a familiar standard. The DIN EN ISO 14125 is reviewed to expose the challenges using hybrid specimens instead of composites. However, the outcome may incorporate in a new draft-standard.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The objective of this section is to list the used materials, display the test samples, describe the joining technique and define the testing method.

2.1 Applied Materials

A hybrid contains at least two unrelated materials with different mechanical properties. In this case, glass fibre-reinforced polypropylene (*Celstran® CFR-TP PP GF70*) as a thermoplastic composite and a zinc-coated steel (*HX 340 LAD + Z 100MB*) are the applied materials. **Table 1** features the main properties of the materials presented.

Table 1: Properties of the used materials

	Celstran® CFR-TP PP GF70	HX 340 LAD + Z 100MB
Class	Composite: Polypropylene with E-glass	Metal
Tensile Modulus*	33.1 GPa ¹	210 GPa ³
Tensile Strength*	901 MPa ¹	410 - 510 MPa ³
Tensile Strain at Failure*	2.89 % ¹	≥ 21 % ³
Flexural Modulus*	33.2 GPa ²	Isotropic
Flexural Strength*	606 MPa ²	Isotropic
Flexural Strain to Failure*	2.01 % ²	Isotropic

* Tested with different standards: ¹D3039M, ²D790, ³DIN EN ISO 6892

As the last row in **Table 1** indicates, the unrelated materials have individual testing methods, which highlights the need for standardisation especially in case of hybridisation.

However, the polypropylene is a tape with continuous fibres, which are arranged in an unidirectional 0° fibre orientation angle. The fibre volume ratio is 45 % in the entire composite volume.

2.2 Joining Technique

In this paper, a fusion bonding process bonds both materials. A hot tool provides external heat to melt the thermoplastic material and squeezes the molten polymer on the steel's surface. There, the viscous polypropylene solidifies and develops the joint between the composite and the steel. This method allows a more accurate characterisation of the hybrids compared to an adhesively bonded one because the amount of bonding surfaces is reduced.

Nevertheless, a sufficient joint strength claims a couple of preparation steps prior to the joining of the individual adherends to a hybrid multipurpose sample. The steps are individual for each adherend. The composite has only a step. The tape is cut to the size and stacked in the desired fibre orientation angle in a mould. In terms of this paper, the investigation only focuses on composites with an unidirectional 0° fibre orientation angle because fibres provide better mechanical performance when

they are tensile loaded (axis 1 in **Figure 4**). The layer quantity depends on the amount of composite and on the desired overall thickness of the sample. The steel preparation consists of three steps. First, the steel is cut in the size slightly larger than the composite. Second, one side is sandblasted (grain size: 210 - 297 μm) with corundum to enlarge the adhesion area. In the end, the pre-treated surface is wiped with isopropanol to remove corundum remains, which may decrease the joint strength. Then, the steel is placed on the mould with the corundum blasted surface facing the stack of tapes. **Figure 1** shows an exploded view of the adherends and the mould.

Figure 1: Exploded view of mould and adherends

Next, the mould with both adherends is placed in a 195 °C pre-heated hot tool. After six minutes at 13 bar, the heating is turned off respectively, the cooling system is turned on until the mould reaches room temperature. **Figure 2** visualises the temperature and pressure progress during the joining process.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of temperature and pressure progress during the joining process

2.3 Testing Methods

The critical load case for most applied hybrid parts is bending. [23] Consequently, this paper covers the applicability of the bending standard DIN EN ISO 14125, which initially scopes fibre-reinforced plastics. This standard outlines two test setups. For the concern of this paper, the test setup is the four-point test with two supports and two loading noses. The advantages of this procedure

compared to the three-point setup are a constant flexural stress between the noses and no resultant vertical shear forces in the load span (**Figure 3**), which provides a failure not necessarily in the centre of the beam. However, the results of both setups are not comparable but for interested readers [15, 24] deal with the results of hybrid materials tested in the three-point setup.

Figure 3: Shear force and bending moment in the four-point setup

A rectangular test sample rests on two supports and is deflected at a constant crosshead rate (10 mm/min) until failure occurs or a pre-determined deformation (25 mm) is reached. A static ± 30 kN load cell measures the applied force. A position sensor in touch with the sample surface records the deformation between the load span and the sample. **Figure 4** visualises the experimental setup (left: genuine setup, right: idealised setup)

Figure 4: Genuine and idealistic test setup

An universal testing machine (Instron 5960 Series) performs the bending test. The support span is fixed at 75 mm and the load span for the initial series is 25 mm. In an additional test series, the load span varies between 20 mm, 25 mm and 30 mm, so, three span ratios have been investigated. The diameter of the supports and loads noses is 10 mm. The test temperature is 20 °C and the relative humidity is 35 %.

2.4 Test Samples

A water-jet cutting system cuts rectangular test samples (dimensions: 90 mm x 15 mm) from the abovementioned (assembled) hybrid sheet sample. The sample thickness depends on material combinations and only the composite thickness varies between three different configurations. **Table 2** decodes the thickness for all configurations.

Table 2: Nomenclature configurations

Configuration	Overall thickness	Metal thickness	Composite thickness	Number of layers
Composite-dominated	3 mm	1 mm	2 mm	8
Neutral	2 mm	1 mm	1 mm	4
Metal-dominated	1.5 mm	1 mm	0.5 mm	2

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results concerning the different configurations, discusses the sample position and the resulting fracture patterns. Furthermore, the last subsection contains the results of investigations with varying load-to-support-ratio.

3.1 Configuration and Sample Position

Figure 5 shows the results for the different configurations. The force progressions of the three investigated configurations over the deformation during the four point bending test are on the left side. On the right side, the diagrams zoom in at the linear-elastic range. In all charts, a dashed line indicates samples with mainly compression load of the composite and a full line for a mainly tensile loaded composite.

Figure 5: Force progression for different hybrid configurations

The force for the metal-dominated samples (I) increases linear for both load cases and passes over smoothly to the plastic deformation around 2 mm. The progressions differ at 15 mm as the compression loaded samples fail with a continuously decreasing force. The force for tensile loaded samples stagnates around 350 N until the failure occurs. Here, the force decrease is combined with a deformation decrease. A crack at this point leads to an abrupt force decrease which lets the touching sensor bounce, resulting in a negative deformation.

The zoomed diagrams on the right shows for both positions identical force progressions. Using regression analysis shows that the determined linear equation can confirm the equality between both graphs because of similar slopes. In this range, it is possible to extract a characteristic stiffness value to outline the hybrid configuration.

In comparison, samples with a neutral configuration (II) show a similar transition between elastic and plastic area and overall an almost identical tendency. Nevertheless, the force level is higher than before but at the cost of deformation, which decreases around 18 % for compression and 27 % for tensile loaded samples. The slope in the linear-elastic area is again quite similar between both load cases but steeper (approximately 50 %) compared to the metal-dominated configuration. Like previously described, the tension and compression differ in the plastic area for this configuration, however, without the bouncing of the sensor at the breaking point.

A further increase of the composite share (III) strengthens the outlined tendency to embrittlement. While the maximum force doubles to 1200 N to the former neutral configuration and even triples in contrast to the metal-dominated, the deformation almost halves (43 %) itself between the neutral and the composite-dominated configuration.

Samples within the composite-dominated configuration have two linear-elastic areas. The first slope ascends steeply until 2.5 mm. Here, there is no difference between tension and compression. From 2.5 mm onwards, the force ascends in a flatter way with a difference between both load cases. After reaching the maximum, the force drops abruptly in the tensile loaded case. Then, the samples are able to absorb force again, indicating an increase at a short range of deformation. Afterwards, the force descends vertically to zero. For compression, the force decreases at first abruptly and then continuously after the maximum. At the second reduction, the failure initiates a force to bounce the sensor as explained at the metal-dominated.

In comparison to the previous configurations, the slope of composite-dominated samples is the steepest. However, the determined linear regression for both load cases show the slope conformity indicating no influence between the different sample positions in the first linear-elastic force range.

Moreover, the maximum forces for both load cases are different. The tensile case reaches higher forces because the fibre core can absorb forces in their tensile direction.

To sum up, configurations with different proportion of composite to the total thickness show different force progressions and can be identified by this test setup. The composite-dominated configuration has the steepest force increase and the metal-dominated the flattest. The neutral configuration is in between. With regard to the sample position, it can be seen that in the linear elastic range the forces and deformations between predominantly tensile and compression loads of the composite are identical. The plastic deformations are different.

3.2 Fracture Pattern

This section describes the fracture patterns of the three configurations depending on the load case. **Figure 6** contains pictures of tension and compression loaded composites.

Figure 6: Fracture patterns for different configurations

Generally, the failure mode does not depend on the configuration. However, samples mainly loaded with tension fail in the boundary layer. The composite delaminates from the steel, which has a permanent bend. In the composite-dominated configuration, there is a fibre break at the opposite point of a load, in addition to the boundary layer failure. At this point, a crack begins to propagate due to the superposition of the maximal lateral force and maximal bending moment (**Figure 3**) and proceeds to the edges of the sample. However, the spontaneous loss of force in the diagrams in **Figure 5** characterises this delamination or peeling effect. In the case of the composite-dominated samples (**Figure 5, III**), the first drop in the force (at 9 mm tensile load) shows a delamination between steel and composite. The second descend refers to the fibre break, because after this no forces can be transferred via the fibres.

Since there is no failure in the boundary layer, the gradual loss of force in predominantly compression-loaded samples have a different cause. The fracture patterns reflect that the loads push the fibres towards each other and force them to break. As the proportion of composite increases, the crumpled areas increase and the individual layers of the composite successively fail, which explains the gradually decreasing force.

3.3 Variation of Load-to-span-ratio

This section presents the results for the variation of load-to-span-ratio. To preserve the comparability, only the neutral configuration is investigated with the composite touching the supports (so it is mainly tension loaded). **Figure 7** compares the different ratios and shows a similar tendency between the 3:1 and 2.5:1 ratio but differences to the 3.75:1 ratio. However, the image contains results for samples with a continuously touching sensor at the breaking force to ensure a comparability between the different ratios.

Figure 7: Bending force for various ratios

Increasing the load span from 25 mm to 30 mm reduces the load-to-span-ratio from 3:1 to 2.5:1. The comparison between both ratios shows a similar progression. After the similar elastic increase, the force increases to a maximum with an increasing deformation. Shortly afterwards, the force slightly drops for a brief deformation range and suddenly the force falls vertically, which symbolises a fracture. The maximum forces vary between both ratios. The lower ratio reaches around 650 N and is 80 N higher than the initial ratio. Correspondingly, higher bending moments are expected. The influence of load span on the bending moment is represented in **Figure 8**.

Figure 8: Bending moment depending on ratio

Reducing the load span from 25 mm to 20 mm increases the load-to-support-ratio to 3.75:1. The bending force curves differ from the course of the initial series, as shown in **Figure 8**. In comparison, the transition from the elastic to the plastic range is flatter and the force does not drop abruptly at the maximum but decreases continuously. It seems that the needed force level to force a delamination in the boundary layer is not reached. While the composite of 3:1 and 2.5:1 delaminates from the metal sheet (as shown in the first row in **Figure 6**), the samples of the 3.75:1 ratio only have a permanent bend which is shown in **Figure 9**.

Figure 9: Permanent bend of a hybrid sample tested with a 3.75 ratio

In general, there are five failure modes in a hybrid. Three of these failures correspond to the failure of fibre-reinforced plastics and are divided into fibre break, fracture between fibres and delamination of layers in the composite. Furthermore, the metal can fail earlier than the composite. However, this is a theoretical assumption, because it can be assumed that the composite is more brittle than the ductile metal and therefore fails at lower deformations. The last failure mode is failure in the boundary layer between metal and composite.

However, the ratio needs to be fixed at a certain value. A shorter load span approaches the setup of the three-point test and leads to a superposition of the lateral force and bending in the entire sample. This state of stress can be found at real applications but for the determination of a pure bending characteristic, it is not correct. A larger load span reduces the performance of the sample and it does not fail in the boundary layer. Therefore, it is recommended to switch to the ratio of 3:1.

4 CONCLUSION

Since there are no testing standards for hybrids, this paper tests the applicability of the DIN EN ISO 14125 as a composite standard for hybrids. Therefore, different hybrid configurations, sample position and load-to-support-ratios are investigated to indicate the challenges during the adaption of a testing standard.

The test setup allows a distinction between the hybrid configurations, showing distinguishable elastic slopes and different force maximums. Consequently, the identification of unknown hybrid compositions is possible. Moreover, the sample position (whether the composite touches the loads or the supports) does not interfere with the stiffness. This verifies the applied setup because the stiffness should depend on the material characteristics and not on the test setup. As a result, in case of testing stiffness of hybrid materials the sample position does not matter. A determination of strength involves the maximum force, which in turn is determined by the position. This should be taken into account especially when the sample is composite-dominant.

Furthermore, the experimental setup can be optimised. The arrangement of the sensor is unfortunate because the individual spans for the loads and the supports could not be adjusted as provided by the standard. In addition, the bouncing position sensor records negative deformations. Instead, the usage of an optical system has to be determined to measure the deformation.

However, it is possible to apply the four point bending test from the DIN EN ISO 14125 to test hybrids. Unfortunately, the investigations are not sufficient to develop a valid standard for hybrids because further material combinations for both adherends need to be investigated as well as different

pre-treatment methods of the steel adherend. In addition, neither the influence of the test speed, nor the temperature nor the moisture content were investigated.

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